

MAJESTIC TEA CAFÉ – A FEASIBILITY STUDY

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Abstract. This study was done to determine the feasibility of the Majestic Tea Cafe in San Carlos City, Pangasinan. The result shows that the respondents who are also prospective customers of this business are in favor of Majestic Tea Cafe in San Carlos City, Pangasinan. Furthermore, the respondents believe that there is still a need to adapt the COVID-19 protocols for the safety of human beings. This study was an attempt to find out which milk tea shop has the best marketing in attracting and satisfying our customers. The purpose of this paper is to find out the level of satisfaction of the customers with the products sold and the marketing strategies used by the selected Milk Tea Shops in the city. After coding the result of 150 respondents from San Carlos City, Pangasinan which are 60 males and 90 females, the data revealed that all of the respondents who are also prospective customers are in favor of the Majestic Tea Cafe business to be established in San Carlos City, Pangasinan. The study gives the consumer an affordable product with health benefits. This also allows the customer to engage in a business that will serve as a stepping stone to economic growth. Furthermore, this feasibility study also serves as a guide and stepping stone to economic growth. This study helps to further progress the Majestic Tea Cafe and have good results for our customers.

Keywords. Milk Tea, Feasibility Study, Customer Behaviour

1 Introduction

1.1 Rationale

Milk tea is one of the trends and the most purchased beverage at present. Milk tea is popular not just because of its health benefits, but also because of its unique taste, no wonder why a lot of customers are addicted to it. It is a combination of milk and tea, which also comes with different flavors and ingredients. There are variants that customers can choose from. New generations of customers fell in love with this new trend of product. With that, entrepreneurs consider this as a huge opportunity to raise income as well as develop new and unique products out of the original ones. Just like coffee shops, milk tea shops are good venues for people to hang out, socialize, and spend their free time (Ichimura, 2019).

The history of Milk Tea originated in Taiwan and is credited as the birthplace of milk tea. It's one of the largest tea markets in the world, but traditional Taiwanese tea houses faced a decline, as their products only appealed to the older generation. To combat this, tea houses had to come up with innovative ways to attract younger patrons. The first solution was the "tea art house", which emerged around the 1970s. Tea art houses made the act of serving tea a performance, giving extra attention to the quality of the tea leaves, cups, serving utensils, and even the temperature of the water. It proved to be a big hit, as customers were willing to pay high prices to drink their tea (Siy, 2020).

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The researchers conducted this study because it has been observed that a huge of customers are patronizing milk tea shops regularly. There are many factors affecting the number of customers It may be the different influences to the customers in choosing a milk tea brand. Possibly, the marketing strategies used by these selected successful milk tea shops, which the researchers will be focusing on.

In the United States of America, boba tea or bubble tea has existed since the 1990s. One of the things that has made bubble tea so attractive, especially in a country like the USA whose citizens primarily drink coffee, is that bubble tea is so versatile. Bubble tea can come in an assortment of flavors with such a wide range of ingredients; and the options only keep increasing as more shops open, vying to win customers over with innovative, fresh, and unique drinks or sweets

featuring boba. Once just a cold, tea drink with foam and tapioca pearls, bubble tea has expanded to include so much more. Besides, boba tea has expanded to include mocha and coffee-flavored bubble teas so now, you don't even need to choose (Tooker, 2020).

According to (Wertz 2016), Hong Kong-style milk tea is made of a mix of several types of black tea (the proportion of which is usually a "commercial secret" for those famous milk tea sellers), evaporated milk, and sugar, the last of which is added by the customers themselves unless in the case of takeaway. The common advertising catchphrase for milk tea in Hong Kong is "Ceylon black tea with Holland Black & White evaporated milk".

In Japan, royal milk tea is a popular drink usually made with Assam or Darjeeling tea leaves. Although the name comes from the English word for tea, compared to a typical English breakfast tea with milk, royal milk tea has a much higher milk ratio and a sweeter taste (Warwick, 2022).

Filipinos usually are fond of refreshing drinks such as the all-time favorite buko juice and samalamig. But just recently, a new product entered the picture. In a sweep, milk tea captured every Filipino's taste buds from the North to the South. Wherever you go, you would see stalls and café offering milk teas of varying flavors. The fastest-growing milk tea brand in Asia, Gong Cha enjoys huge popularity in the Philippines, with numerous branches around the country. It's the best milk tea shop for anyone who loves winter melon. Customers rave about the Milk Winter melon, Gong Cha's signature blend with sweet, cheesy, and salty cream on top (Kikoy, 2015).

Here in San Carlos City, it seems like the same for the typical Filipino who loves Milk Tea, especially the student. I Love Milk Tea is one of the popular Coffee shops located on Palaris Street, San Carlos City listed under Grocery Store in San Carlos City, Food/grocery in San Carlos City. Aside from Milk Tea products, I Love Milk Tea also offers Milk teas, Nachos, Pizza, Fruit Tea, and Frappe. I Love Milk Tea was established in September 2018. I Love Milk Tea is a full business establishment that can accommodate customers with its seating capacity.

In Majestic Tea Café is a shop that has a Photo Booth by Instax. Instax is a series of instant cameras and Smartphone printers that is widely popular among Gen Z and Millennial users. We would like to offer this kind of Photo Booth and give customers Instax photos that include a template with the date of their when they visit our shop. The target customer in our Majestic Tea Cafe is students, and people who love to drink Milk Tea. Aside from Milk Tea and Sandwiches, this shop offers a special Menu for customers like, Breakfast Roll sandwich, Pita sandwiches, Chicken Salad, Veggie and Hummus, Kentucky Hot Brown, Ham and cheese, Nachos, Veggie Stir - Fried noodles, and more. Of course, free use of internet access. We would like to offer this kind of Milk Tea shop in San Carlos City, Pangasinan because nowadays Milk Tea is trendy not only for students but also for people who love to drink Milk Tea. So that our customers will enjoy our snacks and drinks together with their friends, family, and loved ones.

1.2 Research Design

This chapter provides pointers for handling this ambivalence in the design of a qualitative research project. The researcher gathered the data that was needed for the study. This study will be conducted to assess the target customers of Majestic Tea Cafe. To satisfy the objectives of the study, descriptive research was held. To be able to gather the necessary data, the researcher utilizes the descriptive. The researcher chose simple random sampling to randomly select respondents from San Carlos City, Pangasinan. The questionnaires were administered to collect information to target customers of Majestic Tea Cafe

Descriptive research was used by the researchers in the study because this type of research design in qualitative emphasizes the objective of measuring and describing phenomena. Research design is the conceptual blueprint within which research is conducted. Researchers for this research prepare an action plan, which constitutes the outline of the collection, measurement, and analysis of data. Research design is not associated with any particular technique of data collection or any particular type of data. When designing research, we must recognize the type of evidence required to answer the research question reasonably.

1.3 Sources of Data

The respondents of this study were Male and Female the selected residents of San Carlos City, Pangasinan. Mostly, the respondents will be those students who love to drink Milk Tea. And also, those people who love to visit Milk Tea shop. The researcher's first choice of the population is the selected residents of San Carlos City, Pangasinan. The researchers gathered information through a survey questionnaire that we prepared for our respondents.

2 Marketing Aspects

The Majestic Tea Cafe is a shop that has a delicious taste of milk tea, frappe an iced beverage that could partner with the hot weather of the Philippines, and a fruit smoothie for refreshment. Also, the customer could choose how much ice or sugar they want on their orders and they can also order healthy snacks like sandwiches and more. One of the business goals is to offer affordable milk tea and on-the-go meals for teenagers and adults around the city. We collaborate with different Online Food Delivery Services in town so that we can accept Online Orders for the convenience of our customers. Giving satisfaction and a newly tasted refreshing milk tea while considering the health of the customers.

Majestic Tea Cafe is a shop aimed to provide customers with quality at a reasonable and just price. Our company targets students and young professionals, As a newcomer in the Milktea market, Majestic Tea Cafe seeks to come up with products that will distinct us from our competitors, a product that provides satisfaction, quality taste, and a new variety of Milktea and also we can offer a Snacks like Sandwiches and more in Majestic Tea Cafe. As time passes and as the popularity of milk tea grows many competitors are entering the market. Majestic Tea Cafe aims to shift customers' unawareness to awareness through advertising, to build up sales through our new product, and to build and establish a strong reputation in the milk tea industry. The main focus was the customers in San Carlos City, Pangasinan. It was also focused on travelers who pass through San Carlos City.

3 Technical Aspects

The technical aspect of Majestic Tea Cafe states the operational flow of the project and the analysis of various factors that affect its technical and operational activities. This includes the production process, storage operation, equipment, machinery, and furniture and fixtures. Others include the floor plan and building and location of the proposed business. The factors explain how a strategic plan will be put into business. Technical or operation planning solves business problems with creative solutions that will maximize the value of resources. This contains how the activity of the business will be used, the desired outcomes, and the process for maintaining the progress of the business. It also provides business analysis management services and strategies.

3.1 Location

Figure 1. Proposed Location

Our group has decided to choose this location and we prefer to rent a commercial space like this with a 5 thousand pesos monthly rental fee. We know that here in San Carlos, it is considered to be the best place to do business. In this space, maybe we need to renovate it and have some concrete installation for our desired Milk Tea shop design. This means always having the best and most efficient facilities, processes, and people. To achieve this, Concrete Installation is investing in many ways that will pay off in competitive advantages for our customers.

Majestic Tea Cafe's overall strategy will be based on a continuing improvement process of setting objectives, measuring results, and providing feedback to facilitate further growth and progress. Concrete Installation has developed sophisticated formwork solutions for some of the most complex construction projects being done today. Our Milk Tea shop standard form systems are versatile and completely adaptable to a variety of configurations such as Y-walls, shafts, and circular walls. The Concrete Installation system can be adapted to almost any construction requirement that calls for forming. We must have an expert staff who can design and manufacture any custom component or accessory item that may be required to complete our desired Milk Tea shop ambiance.

We also have realized substantial savings in labor and material costs by using structural contour construction methods, systems, and equipment. It includes commercial and residential structures. The Renovation of the space has proceeded at a red-hot pace for several years running. A record of almost 50 thousand pesos for its renovation costs including already for the materials needed.

This makes for an excellent opportunity to expand Concrete Installation operations and gain significant market share in its primary target market segment. The Milk Tea shop also plans to focus to a lesser extent on the residential and heavy construction for the space renovation which is also very robust at the moment. Our Milk Tea Shop plans to rapidly develop marketing alliances and pursue new sales of its services to residential and commercial here in town. The market strategy is to capitalize on Concrete Installation's alliances by securing our preferred Milk Tea Shop Space.

Location Advantage:

- 5 – 10 minutes away from OLD and NEW Public Market, CSI, City Mall, Magic Mall & San Carlos Town Center
- Has a Parking lot
- Along the road, transportation is easy
- Safe & secured, very accessible
- Near SCC, (aside from schools, near a Fast Food chain)
- For Long Term & Short Term

3.2 Layout / Floor Plan

Figure 2. Proposed Floor Plan

The plan layout is tactically designed to support the smooth process of the proposed Milk Tea shop. The food preparation area is a place where all the finished products that are ready to sell are displayed. The work table will be the area where the milk tea and other foods will be made by the barista. This floor plan helps to provide a good plan and design for the renovation of our milk tea shop in San Carlos City Pangasinan.

4 Management Aspects

This chapter shows the form of business organization, organizational structure, personnel needed, and job specifications and qualifications of the employees for the operation of the business. Personnel's duties and responsibilities will be discussed in this chapter.

Figure 3. Organizational Chart

A chief executive officer (CEO) - is the top position in an organization and is responsible for implementing existing plans and policies, improving the company's financial strength, supporting ongoing digital business transformation, and setting the future strategy of Majestic Tea Cafe.

Accounting Manager - the overall management and supervision of the accounting department. This includes overseeing the work of accountants, reviewing financial statements, and preparing reports for upper management. They may also develop and implement accounting policies and procedures.

Office managers - are responsible for keeping an office running smoothly and overseeing administrative support. The job can range widely in duties and responsibilities, from reception, copy editing, and support, to handling a specific type of paperwork or filing for a specific department.

Sales Manager - usually includes building and leading a team of salespeople to help drive revenue. Sales managers must motivate their teams to generate leads, build client relationships, set targets to hit or exceed revenue forecasts, and ultimately meet customer needs.

Sales Associate - is usually responsible for welcoming customers, maintaining floor appearance, directing customers to goods, and operating cash registers. They ensure that their company makes more sales and gets customers products suited to their needs.

5 Financial Aspect

This chapter shows and discusses the financial forecast for the proposed Majestic Tea Cafe including the financial assumptions, the investment costs, the financial statements and the financial analysis, balance sheets, and cash flow. Moreover, this chapter also summarizes the source and uses of funds.

5.1 Financial Assumptions

1. Sales are expected to increase by 10% annually.
2. The rent contract will be P8,000.00 monthly, with a term 1-month advance and a 1-month deposit as per the contract.
3. Kitchen and store supplies are assumed to be consumable within a year and will increase by 5% respectively.
4. All products not sold within five days will be pulled out from the glass display or freezer. The allowable waste will be .005 of gross sales for the first year since the business is still new and management is not yet familiar with how to manage the inventory. Spoilage will constantly decrease by .0025 in the following years.
5. Electricity and water expense was assumed to increase by 5% annually because of increasing electricity bill
6. Delivery Expense was assumed to increase by 5% annually due to the fluctuating cost of oil
7. The marketing budget will increase by 5% annually.
8. Salaries and Wages will increase by 10% annually implemented by the owner as a reward for the employee's hard work and commitment to their job.
9. The store assumes that it will always have P50,000.00 on its cash on hand. There will also be withdrawals, P250,000.00 for the first year, and will increase by P50,000.00 annually. Moreover, the remaining cash is deposited in a current account in a certain bank. Interest income on the current account is considered immaterial and irrelevant to decision-making and, therefore, not included in the financial statement.
10. The store will allot a P1000.00 load allowance per month to ensure good communication between the employer, employee, and customer.
11. The store will have a 5% allowance for repairs and maintenance based on the carrying value of the machinery and equipment.

5.1 Cash Flow Statement

The first of our financial statements examples is the cash flow statement. The cash flow statement shows the changes in a company's cash position during a fiscal period. The cash flow statement uses the net income figure from the income statement and adjusts it for non-cash expenses. This is done to find the change in cash from the beginning of the period to the end of the period.

The cash flow statement begins with the net income and adjusts it for non-cash expenses, changes to balance sheet accounts, and other usages and receipts of cash. The adjustments are grouped under operating activities, investing activities, and financing activities.

Table 1. Projected Cost

Projected	Amount
Cash	50,000.00
Beginning Inventory	90,976.00
Prepaid Rent	20,000.00
Machinery and Equipment	91,945.00
Furniture and Fixture	51,345.00
Pre - Operating Expenses	10,000.00
Operating Expenses (12 months)	48,478.00
TOTAL:	P 362,744

Table 2. Pre-Operating Expense and Operating Expense

Operating Expense	Amount
Salaries	25,550.00
Employee Benefits	3,300.00
Store and sanitary supplies	5,000.00
Total:	33,850.00

The following are explanations for the line items listed in the Majestic Tea Cafe's cash flow statement. Please note that certain items such as "Other operating expenses, net" are often defined differently by different companies.

Investing Activities

Purchases of property and equipment purchases of plants, property, and equipment are usages of cash. A deduction from net cash. Proceeds from property and equipment incentives: This line is added for additional detail on Majestic Tea Cafe property and equipment purchases. Incentives received from property and equipment vendors are recorded as a reduction in Amazon's costs and thus a reduction in cash usage.

Supplemental Cash Flow Information:

Cash paid for interest on long-term debt: cash usage to pay the accumulated interest from long-term debt. Cash paid for interest on capital and finance lease obligations: cash usage to pay the accumulated interest from capital and finance lease obligations.

Cash paid for income taxes, net of refunds: cash usage to pay income taxes. Property and equipment acquired under capital leases: the value of property and equipment acquired under new capital leases in the fiscal period. Property and equipment acquired under build-to-suit leases: the value of property and equipment acquired under new build-to-suit leases in the fiscal period.

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6 Socio-Economic Aspect

This chapter discusses the benefits of the proposed business and how the business affects the economy, household, society, and government. It stated also the contribution of the business to the economy and the relevance of it to society. This should be considered by the business to attain positive feedback from the community. The business should not only be concerned about its profit but also about the effect of it on the people and the condition of society.

Effects of the Business the Society

Society refers to the group of people living together in organized communities with shared laws, traditions, and values. The Majestic Tea Cafe will play a part in society because it will affect the government and the household. Our shop will give contributions to them that are beneficial on their part.

Effects on the Government

The government is a political system that is in charge of administering and regulating a specific community or the country itself. By that, they are concerned with all circumstances that affect the country. One of the tourism which can help in the growth of our country. Tourism is a major source of income for many countries. It is advantageous if a lot of people are visiting our country because of some tourist attractions like cafes and other beautiful places; it will have higher economic growth.

The proposed business can be an additional tourist attraction in San Carlos City, Pangasinan. Foreigners having a vacation and also local people may be urged to visit the place. The business can contribute to the tourism development of the city. Moreover, the government needs revenue to defray its expenses and that is why they impose tax on persons, properties, and also businesses. The government and the taxpayers can benefit from this matter. Also, the business is required to pay various Local Taxes and Fees that will be used to support the activities of the locals for its people.

Effects on the Household

Families and businesses have often been treated as naturally separate institutions, but in reality, they are inextricably intertwined. The family has implications for the emergence of new business opportunities, opportunity recognition, business start-up decisions, and the resource mobilization process. Thus, this performance, or what its citizens produced and whether they produced these items within its borders. Since the business will provide new opportunities for a good investment; it will surely increase the said two economic measurements. A good GDP and GNP signify a good standard of living in a certain country.

Contribution to the Economy

The Majestic Tea Cafe will benefit the economy by providing employment. This will give the hired employees and their families their source of income for their living needs. Attracting and growing businesses strengthens our Majestic Tea Cafe providing locally-produced goods and services to customers.

Contribution to the Government

Majestic Tea Cafe will pay its tax obligation as provided by law. Tax will help the government generate funds for the improvement of the public service in San Carlos City Pangasinan.

Contribution to the society

The Majestic Tea Cafe business will provide to help our community. We recognize the nature of business, especially the corporate focus on quality and affordable products and services of the Milk Tea shop which gives a unique opportunity to make a very positive contribution to the society and community that we serve.

7 Summary, Conclusion, and Recommendation

Milk tea shops have become popular nationwide, especially in San Carlos City, Pangasinan. Majestic Tea Cafe is one of the businesses to be introduced in the city. After coding the result of 150 respondents from San Carlos City, Pangasinan which are 60 males and 90 females, the data revealed that all of the respondents who are also prospective customers are in favor of the Majestic Tea Cafe business to be established in San Carlos City, Pangasinan.

These prospective customers are mostly from San Carlos City and some are from neighboring municipalities like Aguilar, Calasiao, Malasiqui, and Urbiztondo Majority of them are students, followed by employed and unemployed people.

Prospect customers have different preferences when buying Milk Tea. The result showed that taste is what the majority of customers considered which is (49%), followed by price (25%), location (11%), ambiance (8%) brand (1%), and (09) others.

